

Editorial

The Stand of the International Journal of Information Studies and Libraries (IJISL) on Upholding Publication Ethics and Combating Research Misconduct

Research misconduct, encompassing falsification, fabrication, and plagiarism, poses significant challenges to the integrity of scholarly publications. In this editorial note, we emphasize the crucial importance of upholding publication ethics and implementing effective measures to combat research misconduct.

Falsification, the intentional manipulation or distortion of data or research outcomes, undermines the very essence of scientific inquiry. Such misconduct not only misleads readers but also erodes the trustworthiness of academic scholarship. As a responsible scholarly journal, it is our duty to implement rigorous double-blind peer-review processes and foster a culture of transparency, ensuring that only authentic and reliable research is published in the International Journal of Information Studies and Libraries (IJISL).

Fabrication, an extreme form of misconduct involving the complete invention of data or results, represents a severe breach of academic integrity. Fabricated research not only impedes scientific progress but also threatens the credibility of the entire scholarly community. At IJISL, we recognize the need for robust mechanisms to detect and prevent fabrication, including engagement of expert reviewers, and adherence to strict editorial policies. By diligently scrutinizing submissions, analyse additional datasets, survey questionnaire and sampling mechanism; we aim to protect the credibility and reputation of the journal.

Plagiarism, another form of research misconduct, undermines the principles of originality and attribution. Unauthorized use or appropriation of others' work, ideas, or words without proper acknowledgment not only violates ethical guidelines but also infringes upon the rights of the original authors. IJISL is committed to maintaining the highest standards of academic integrity by actively combating plagiarism. We employ advanced plagiarism detection tools and rely on the expertise of our reviewers to identify and address instances of plagiarism. Furthermore, we strive to educate authors about proper citation practices, fostering a culture of responsible scholarship.

In conclusion, the International Journal of Information Studies and Libraries (IJISL) takes publication ethics and the prevention of research misconduct seriously. By implementing rigorous editorial practices, promoting transparency, and adhering to strict ethical guidelines, we aim to uphold the integrity of scholarly research. We encourage authors, reviewers, and readers to join us in this collective effort to safeguard the credibility of academic scholarship and foster an environment that promotes genuine knowledge dissemination in the field of library and information science.

Best Wishes

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